

The Kinetic Study of the Solvent Effect of Tertiary Butanol on the Thermodynamic Extensive Properties of Acid Catalysed Hydrolysis of Iso-Butyl Formate

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Received: Jul 28, 2025

Accepted: Aug 25, 2025

Published: Aug 31, 2025

ABSTRACT

The kinetic study of acid catalysed solvolysis of iso-butyl formate has been performed in aquo-t-butanol reaction media having different concentration of t-butanol (tertiary alcohol) from 20 to 80% (v/v) and at different temperatures ranging from 20 to 40°C.

The depletion and enhancement observed respectively in iso-composition and iso-dielectric activation energies reveal that the transition state is solvated and initial state is desolvated with addition of t-butanol in reaction media.

Almost unity value of the slope of the plots of $\log k$ values against $\log [H^+]$ values shows that the reaction follows $A_{AC}2$ mechanism. From the values of iso-kinetic temperature, which comes to be 286.0, it may be concluded that in water-t-butanol reaction media, the reaction follows Barclay-Butler rule and there is weak but acceptable interaction between solvent and solute.

KEYWORDS: Protic Solvent, tertiary alcohol, Substituted Formate, Iso-dielectric, Iso-kinetic, specific solvation, Leffler's rule, Desolvation, Solvent-solute interaction, Mechanistic pathways.

INTRODUCTION

Various kineticists¹⁻⁴ have reported in their works on the solvent effect of dipolar aprotic solvents like DMSO, DMF, Dioxan on the acid

catalysed hydrolysis of aliphatic formate, but the studies on the solvent effect of the tertiary alcohol on the biochemical potential of Iso-butyl formate have not been communicated yet.

Hence it is thought essential to study the solvent effect of a tertiary alcohol t-butanol on the acid catalysed hydrolysis of Iso-butyl formate, as its biochemical use as fumigate and insecticides seems to be very useful in the agriculture and also in cloths and leather industries.

EXPERIMENTAL & CALCULATION

Export quality of Iso-Butyl formate of Fluka grade packed in Switzerland and Merk grade of high purity were used. The kinetics of reaction was studied by adding 0.65 ml of ester through a German make graduated syringe pipette into 50ml of 0.5 M solution of HCl. The reaction was found to obey the first order kinetic equation and the evaluated values of specific rate constants have been recorded in Table – I. The variation of $\log k$ values with mol% of t-butanol have been tabulated in Table – II and variation of $\log k$ with $\log [H_2O]$ of the reaction media are recorded in Table – III. From the slopes of the plots of $\log k$ versus $\log [H_2O]$, the number of water molecules associated with the transition state of the reaction have been evaluated and are placed in Table – IV.

The values of both the iso-composition and iso-dielectric activation energies have been enlisted in Table – V and Table – VI respectively. The numerical values of thermodynamic activation parameters were calculated by using Wynne-Jones & Eyring equation⁵ and are synchronised in Table – VII. Effect of change in $[H^+]$ ion concentration of the reaction media on the specific rate constants of the reaction has been shown in Table – VIII.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Table – I shows that the rate constant values of the reaction decrease with increasing proportion of t-butanol in the reaction media. On plotting $\log k$ values against mol% of t-butanol (from recorded values in Table – II), it is obvious that up to 17.80 mol% of t-butanol in the reaction media, the rate of reaction falls rapidly but beyond (above) 17.80mol% of t-butanol, the depletion in the rate follows slow path. From the slope, it is also apparent that with increase in temperature of the reaction, the rate of reaction decreases more sharply. The decreasing trend in the values of the specific rate constants needs to be discussed in the light of Hughes and Ingold⁶ predictions according to which an increase in the dielectric constant values of the reaction media causes an increase in the rate when there is concentration or constructions of charges on the transition state and causes a decrease in the rate when there is diffusion or destruction of charges on the transition state.

The values of dielectric constants of the reaction media go on decreasing with gradual addition of t-butanol. So the findings are fully in accordance with the qualitative prediction of Hughes and Ingold⁶. However, these findings are in agreement with the qualitative prediction of Laidler and Landskroener⁷ and also with the earlier views of Singh

and Sweety *et al.*⁸ and also with the recent reports of Renu & Singh *et al.*⁹, who predicted that the rate of ion-dipolar reaction decreases with the decrease in the dielectric constant values of the reaction media.

Evaluation of number of water molecules involved in the formation of activated complex of the reaction and mechanism of reaction:

Robertson¹⁰ has derived an equation, which is as:

$$\log k = \log k' + n \log[H_2O]$$

where 'n' is the salvation number, i.e., the number of water molecules associated with the transition state of the reaction and is evaluated from the slopes of the plots of $\log k$ versus $\log[H_2O]$.

Robertson *et al.*¹¹ suggested that value of 'n' for unimolecular reactions is fairly high while that of bimolecular reactions, it will be low.

From the recorded values of $\log k$ and $\log[H_2O]$ in Table – III, the $\log k$ values were plotted against $\log[H_2O]$ and the evaluated values of the slopes of the straight lines have been enlisted in Table – IV.

From the plots, it is clear that at each temperature two intersecting straight lines are obtained at $\log[H_2O]$ value - 1.414 which corresponds to 46.70% of water concentration (v/v) in aquo-t-butanol reaction media.

From the recorded values of the slopes of the plots of $\log k$ versus $\log[H_2O]$ in Table – III, it is clear that below or before $\log[H_2O]$ value 1.414, which corresponds to 46.70% of water in the reaction media, the number of water molecules associated with the activated complex increases from 0.194 to 0.715 with increase in temperature of the reaction from 20 to 40°C. Similarly, for above 46.70% water concentration in the reaction media, the number of water molecules involved in the formation of the activated complex

increases from 0.463 to 1.394 with rise in temperature from 20 to 40°C.

Overall, it is concluded that number of water molecules associated with the activated complex increases from 0.194 to 1.394 with rise in temperature from 20°C to 40°C and from this trend, in the light of the guidelines of Robertson *et al.*¹¹, it is inferred that the mechanistic pathway of the reaction is changed from bimolecular to unimolecular with increase in water concentration or with decrease in t-butanol content of the reaction media and also with increase in the temperature of the reaction.

From enhancing trend of number of water molecules involved in the formation of the activated complex, it is also inferred that on addition of t-butanol in the reaction media, the equilibrium of water is shifted from its dense form to bulky form.

Such observations and inferences and have been earlier reported by Priyanka & Singh *et al.*¹² and also recently by Lal & Singh *et al.*¹³.

Solvent Effect on Iso-composition Activation energy (E_c) of the Reaction:

From the slopes of Arrhenius plots of $\log k$ versus $10^3/T$, the values of iso-composition activation energy (E_c) of the reaction have been evaluated and are tabulated in Table – V. From Table – V, it is obvious that E_c values go on decreasing from 105.23 to 67.19 kJ/mol with increasing the concentration of t-butanol from 20 to 80% (v/v) in reaction media. This trend is probably due to solvation changes taking place either at initial state level or at the transition state level or at the level of both the initial and transition states as reported earlier by Elsemongy *et al.*¹⁴ in this field. Considering the extent of solvation to be a dominant factor, the following three factors seem to be responsible for decrease in E_c

values with gradual addition of t-butanol in the reaction media:

- (i) The transition state is solvated and the initial state is desolvated.
- (ii) The transition state is desolvated less than the initial state, and
- (iii) The transition state is solvated more than the initial state

The transition state being large cation (ester +H⁺) is available more for solvation by t-butanol molecule than the initial state, so the first factor seems to be operative in this case and it is also supported by the decrease in entropy of activation (ΔS^*) of the reaction as shown in Table – VII. So situation first is more plausible explanation for decrease in E_c values of the reaction as recorded in Table – V.

It is, therefore, inferred that E_c values of the reaction go on decreasing due to solvation of the transition state and desolvation of initial state. Similar interpretations for depletion in E_c value have also been reported earlier by Singh & Hafizee *et al.*¹⁵ and recently by Sushma & Singh *et al.*¹⁶.

Effect of Solvent on the Iso-dielectric Activation energy (E_D) of the Reaction:

With a view to minimise the dielectric effect, the iso-dielectric activation energy was evaluated from the slopes of the Arrhenius plots of $\log k_D$ values (obtained from interpolation of plots of $\log k$ values against D values of the reaction media) against $1/T$. The values thus obtained have been tabulated in Table – VI. From the Table – VI, it is found that E_D values go on increasing from 80.19 to 111.26 kJ/mol with increase in D values from $D = 20$ to $D = 60$. This trend of increase in E_D values is quite in agreement with changes (decrease) in E_c values of this reaction and also with the findings of Wolford¹⁷ and with the earlier findings

of Monalisa & Singh *et al.*¹⁸. However, recently Prashansa & Singh¹⁹ have also reported similar interpretations for the changes in Iso-dielectric Activation energy (E_D) of the solvolysis reactions.

Solvent Effect on Thermodynamic Activation Parameters of the Reaction:

The three thermodynamic activation parameters namely enthalpy of activation (ΔH^*), entropy of activation (ΔS^*) and the free energy of activation (ΔG^*) of the reaction were evaluated using Wynne-Jones and Eyring equation⁵ and have been mentioned in Table – VII. From the values enlisted in Table – VII, it is clear that ΔG^* values of the reaction go on increasing with simultaneous decrease in both the ΔH^* and ΔS^* values of the reaction.

In order to study the variations in these thermodynamic parameters more clearly, these were plotted against mol% of t-butanol. From their plots, it is clear that ΔH^* , ΔG^* and ΔS^* vary non-linearly to the considerable extent with the increasing concentration (mol%) of t-butanol and this is the indication of specific solvation taking place in the reaction media according to Saville and Hudson²⁰.

The ΔH^* and ΔS^* are complimentary to each other as the resulting net property of ΔG^* in Table – VII is a well behaved function. From the values of ΔG^* in Table – VII, it is clear that ΔG^* is being little affected by the solvent composition (mol%). However there is considerable enhancement (from 87.72 to 89.97 kJ/mol at 30°C) in ΔG^* values.

From Table – VII, it is also clear that ΔG^* values are found to increase simultaneously with depletion in both the ΔH^* and ΔS^* values.

From the thermodynamic relation:

$$\Delta G^* = \Delta H^* - T\Delta S^*$$

it is apparent that enhancement in ΔG^* values with simultaneous decrease in both of ΔH^* and ΔS^* values of the reaction is only possible when the extent of depletion in ΔS^* values is greater than in ΔH^* values. From these findings, it is concluded that the acid catalysed hydrolysis of Iso-butyl formate in aquo-t-butanol media is entropy controlled and enthalpy dominating reaction.

Similar findings and inferences have also been reported earlier by Kumar & Singh *et al.*²¹ and recently by Sabita & Singh²².

Solvent Effect on Solvent-Solute Interaction in the Aquo-T-butanol Reaction media:

For highlighting solvent-solute interaction for a solvolysis reaction, Barclay and Butler²³ have correlated the enthalpy of activation (ΔH^*) and the entropy of activation (ΔS^*) by means of the relationship:

$$\delta m(\Delta H^*) = \beta \delta m(\Delta S^*)$$

where, β is a constant called iso-kinetic temperature and it is evaluated from the slope of plots of ΔH^* values against ΔS^* value.

From the recorded values of ΔH^* and ΔS^* in Table – VII, ΔH^* values were plotted against ΔS^* (at 30°C). The plot consists of a straight line whose slope values has been evaluated to be $285.86 \approx 286.0$ which is less than 300. On the guidelines of Leffler²⁴, it is concluded that there is weak but considerable solvent-solute interaction for acid catalysed hydrolysis of Iso-butyl formate in aquo-t-butanol reaction media.

Similar interpretations for solvent-solute interaction have also been reported earlier by Singh & Kumari *et al.*²⁵ and recently by Sabita & Singh R. T.²⁶.

Effect of Change of $[H^+]$ in concentration of the Reaction Media:

In order to investigate the effect of change in acid concentration of the reaction media (H^+ in concentration) on the acid catalysed hydrolysis of Iso-butyl formate in aquo-t-butanol media, experiments were performed to study the kinetics at various concentration of HCl (from 0.1M to 0.8M), keeping the temperature, solvent composition and ionic strength of the reaction media constant. The reactions were carried out at 25° C in the reaction media having 20% (v/v) concentration of t-butanol and the evaluated values of specific rate constants have been tabulated in Table – VIII. From the tabulated values of log k and log $[H^+]$ in Table – VIII, log k values were plotted against log $[H^+]$ and it is clear that the plot is an excellent straight line showing linear dependence of rate of reaction on $[H^+]$ ion concentration. The slope of the log k versus log $[H^+]$ plot is evaluated to be 0.998 which is almost equal to unity. From this value of slope (unity), it may be inferred on the basis of the hypothesis of Zucker and Hammett²⁷ that acid catalysed hydrolysis of Iso-butyl formate in aquo-t-butanol media follows A_{AC}^2 mechanism.

Similar conclusions have also been reported earlier by Singh and Jha *et al.*¹⁻², and in recently by Ashutosh & Singh²⁸, Raghaw & Singh *et al.*²⁹ and Anant & Singh *et al.*³⁰.

References:

- Singh, Lallan, Singh, R.T., and Jha, R.C. : J. Indian Chem. Soc.,**57**, 1089, 1980
- Singh, Lallan, Singh, R.T., and Jha, R.C. : J. Indian Chem. Soc.,**58**, 966, 1981
- Kumari Sunita, Kumar S. and Singh R. T.: WHJJ, **XV**, No. (IX), 125-140, Sept. 2020
- K. Priyanka, K. Raghaw, Namrata and Singh R. T.: WHJJ, **XVI**, No. (IX), 97-100, Sept. 2020
- Wynne- Jones W. F. K. and Eyring, H.: J. Chem. Phys., **3**, 492, 1953
- Hughes E. D. and Ingold C. K. : J. Chem. Soc., **244**, 255, 1935
- Laidler, K.J. and Lanskroener, P.A. : Trans Faraday Soc. **52**, 200, 1956
- Singh & K Sweety, Ranjan N and Singh R. T., ARJ Phys. Soc., **17**, Nos. (1-2), 173-185, 2014
- K Renu, Namrata, S. Shweta and Singh R. T.: Aut. Aut. Research Journal, **XI**, No. (XI), 316-327, 2020
- Robertson, R. E.: Prog. Phy. Org. Chem., **52**, 321, 1975
- Robertson, R. E., Heppolitile, R. L. and Scott, J. M. W.: Canad. J. Chem. Soc., **37**, 803, 1969
- Priyanka K., Nazia S., Kumar V. and Singh R. T.: ARJ Phys. Sci., **17**, No. (1-2), 117-128, 2014
- Lal Vikash, K. Kishor, K. Raghaw and Singh R. T.: WHJJ, **XVI**, No. (IX), 141-160, Sept. 2020
- Elsemongy, M.M., Elamayem, M.S. and Moussa, M.N.H. : Z. Physik. Chem. Neue Folge, **95**, 215, 1975
- Singh, R.T., Navendu, K.S., Henry, W. and Hafizee, N.K. : NIRJ. Sci., **14**, 53-61, 2014
- K. Sushma, A. Abhay, Singh R and Singh R. T.: IJAEMA, **XII**, No. (I), 3345-3363, Jan 2020
- Wolford, R. K.: J. Phys. Chem., **67**, 632, 1963
- Monalisa, Singh R. N. Sudhansu, N. S. and Singh R. T.: NIRJ Sci., **12**, 89-100, 2013
- Srivastava P., Singh Y. P., Singh R. T.: Journal of Xidian University, **10**, No. (8), 285-292, 2023
- Saville, B. J. and Hudson, R. F. : J. Chem. Soc., 4114, 1955
- Kumari S., Kumari S., Kumar V. and Singh R. T.: NIRJ Sci., **19**, 49-60, 2015

22. Sabita K and Singh R. T.: Aut. Aut. Research Journal, **XIV**, No. (8), 01-07, Aug. 2023
23. Barclay, I. A. and Butler, J. A. V.: Trans Faraday Soc., **34**, 1445, 1938
24. Leffler J. E. : Org. Chem., **20**, 1201, 1955
25. Singh R. T., Kumari R., Singh P. and Kumari A.: ARJ Phys. Sci., **14**, No. (1-2), 127-135, 2011
26. K. Sabita and Singh R. T.: GIS Science Journal: , **10**, No. (8), 569-573, 2023
27. Zucker L., and Hammett, L. P.: J. Am. Chem. Soc., **61**, 2791, 1939
28. Ashutosh Abhay and Singh R. T.: Journal of Xidian University, **18**, No. (1), 8-16, 2024
29. K. Raghaw and Singh R. T.: Gradiva Review Research Journal, **9**, (No.8), 363-373, 2023
30. K. Anant and Singh R. T.: GIS Science Journal, **12**, No. (1), 139-146, 2025

Table - I
Specific Rate Constants Values of Acid Catalysed Hydrolysis of Iso-Butyl Formate in
Water-t-butanol Media
 $k \times 10^3$ in $(\text{dm})^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$

Temp in °C	% of t-butanol (v/v)						
	20%	30%	40%	50%	60%	70%	80%
20°C	68.83	64.66	60.02	56.29	53.72	50.13	47.38
25°C	141.32	127.67	116.24	93.26	93.26	86.22	74.92
30°C	287.21	269.92	216.37	187.54	151.77	139.60	117.65
35°C	555.60	467.95	394.00	328.70	273.87	224.18	179.85
40°C	1072.26	870.76	716.47	569.51	453.11	363.24	275.93

Table II
Variation of log k values of the reaction at different temperature with mol%
of Iso-Butyl Formate in Water-t-butanol Media

% of t-butanol (v/v)	Mol% of t-butanol	3 + log k values				
		20°C	25°C	30°C	35°C	40°C
20%	04.53	1.8378	2.1502	2.4582	2.7476	3.0303
30%	07.52	1.8093	2.1061	2.3978	2.6702	2.9399
40%	11.23	1.7783	2.0578	2.3352	2.5955	2.8522
50%	15.95	1.7504	2.0154	2.2731	2.5168	2.7555
60%	22.15	1.7069	1.9697	2.2089	2.4375	2.6562
70%	30.68	1.7001	1.9254	2.1449	2.3506	2.5602
80%	43.15	1.6756	1.8746	2.0706	2.2549	2.4408

Table III

Variation of log k values of the reaction with log [H₂O] values of Water-t-butanol system (media) at different temperatures

% of t-butanol	% of H ₂ O	log [H ₂ O]	3+ log k values				
			20°C	25°C	30°C	35°C	40°C
20%	80%	1.6478	1.8378	2.1502	2.4582	2.7476	3.0303
30%	70%	1.5898	1.8093	2.1061	2.3978	2.6702	2.9399
40%	60%	1.5229	1.7783	2.0578	2.3352	2.5955	2.8522
50%	50%	1.4437	1.7504	2.0154	2.2731	2.5168	2.7555
60%	40%	1.3468	1.7069	1.9697	2.2089	2.4375	2.6562
70%	30%	1.2218	1.7001	1.9254	2.1449	2.3506	2.5602
80%	20%	1.0458	1.6756	1.8746	2.0706	2.2549	2.4408

Table - IV

Values of the slopes of the plots of log k versus log [H₂O] at different Temperatures

Temp. in °C	Slope - I when log [H ₂ O] value is below 1.414	Slope - II when log [H ₂ O] value is above 1.414
20°C	0.194	0.463
25°C	0.351	0.730
30°C	0.421	1.048
35°C	0.642	1.214
40°C	0.715	1.394

Table - V

Evaluated Values of Iso-Composition Activation Energy (E_c or E_{exp}) of the reaction in Water-t-butanol Media

% of t-butanol (v/v)	20%	30%	40%	50%	60%	70%	80%
E _c values in kJ/Mol	105.23	99.60	96.82	88.82	82.30	75.66	67.19

Table - VI
Evaluated Values of Iso-Dielectric Activation Energy (E_D) of the reaction at different Desired 'D' Values of the Water-t-butanol Media

D value	D=20	D=30	D=40	D=50	D=60
E_D values in kJ/Mol	80.19	88.23	95.84	103.79	111.26

Table VIII
Effect of $[H^+]$ on the Specific Rate Constant Values of Acid Catalysed Hydrolysis of Iso-Butyl Formate in Water-t-butanol Media at Constant Ionic Strength ($\mu=0.9$)

Concentration of t-butanol=20%
(v/v)

Temp 25°C

$[H^+]$	[KCl]	μ	$k \times 10^3$ in min^{-1}	$2 + \log[H^+]$	$3 + \log k$	Value of the Slope of the Plots of $\log k$ versus $\log [H^+]$
0.10	0.80	0.90	38.86	1.0000	1.4603	
0.15	0.75	0.90	40.63	1.1761	1.6068	
0.20	0.70	0.90	56.65	1.3010	1.7532	
0.25	0.65	0.90	71.15	1.3979	1.8522	
0.30	0.60	0.90	85.09	1.4771	1.9299	0.998
0.40	0.50	0.90	112.23	1.6021	2.0501	
0.50	0.40	0.90	141.32	1.6990	2.1502	
0.60	0.30	0.90	170.33	1.7782	2.2313	
0.70	0.20	0.90	196.43	1.8451	2.2932	
0.80	0.10	0.90	222.89	1.9030	2.3481	

Table VII
Consolidated Values of Activation Parameters (ΔH^* , ΔG^* , ΔS^*) of the reaction in Water-t-butanol System at 30°C

ΔH^* , ΔG^* in kJ/mol and ΔS^* in J/K/ mol

% of t-butanol	mol% of t-butanol	ΔH^* in kJ/Mol	30°C		
			ΔG^*	ΔS^*	(ΔS^*+100)
20%	5.81	102.31	87.72	48.15	148.15
30%	9.56	98.72	88.07	35.15	135.15
40%	14.12	92.76	88.32	14.65	114.65
50%	19.79	86.04	88.79	-12.38	87.62
60%	27.01	80.09	89.16	-20.35	70.65
70%	36.54	72.67	89.54	-55.61	44.39
80%	49.67	66.56	89.97	-77.26	22.74